

Evaluation of the OHEJP cogwheel workshops

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Report from One Health EJP Cogwheels Evaluation

Introduction

Background for the One Health EJP Cogwheels Evaluation initiative: In October 2020 an evaluation of the One Health EJP cogwheel workshops (CWs) was initiated. The aim was to evaluate if the CW concept fits its purpose and to reveal if any improvements or adjustments can be made for future workshops. In total, eight CWs will be arranged during the OHEJP; five workshops had been arranged before the evaluation, one was planned in parallel with the evaluation process, and the two final ones will be arranged in 2021 after results from this evaluation have been made available for implementation.

About the cogwheel concept: In Work Package 4 (WP4) of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that might require strategic interaction with OHEJP are identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops (CWs), are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project Leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRPs) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project, it is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs and to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with databases/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics) and so on. Reports from the CWs are used as part of the input to the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) of WP2, as well as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of WP7.

The survey:

The questionnaire was generated by the Norwegian Veterinary Institute using the Questback essentials program. The questions and format of the questionnaire were developed by the WP4 team in collaboration with WP2 (María Ugarte) and WP3 (Hein Imberechts and Racha ElMounaged). The questionnaire was distributed as a link to 185 email addresses, including Project Leaders, deputy Project Leaders and to the members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and the Project Management Team (PMT) within the OHEJP. The questionnaire invitation was sent the 4th of November 2020, a kind reminder the 16th of November and the questionnaire was finally closed the 17th of November.

Please see the attachment for questions and answers in detail.

The survey received answers from 30 respondents. All respondents did not answer all questions in the questionnaire. The role distribution consisted of seven project leaders, one deputy project leaders, four project WP leaders, five Project task leaders and 18 had other roles. It was possible for one respondent to register with several roles if relevant.

Summary of results:

- 83% (25/30) of the respondents were already aware of the aim with the workshops; “to avoid overlaps between external projects and the OHEJP projects and find synergies”.
- 83% (25/30) of the respondents had been informed about previous CWs.
- 43% (13/30) of the respondents had been consulted to give input for a CW.
- 23% (7/30) of the respondents had not participated in any CW.

- 95% (21/22) of the respondents find the CWs useful. Information about relating projects, avoiding overlaps, build on results from one or more of the target projects, insight into non-connected projects, exchange of information, networking, discussions and gaining general overview of research activities are highlighted as typical positive factors from the concept. One person did not find the CWs useful - no reason for this was given.
- 21% (6/28) of the respondents have contacted the invited external project afterwards.
- 44% (12/27) of the respondents have contacted other EU projects related to the OHEJP, regardless of the CW.
- 96% (24/25) of the respondents confirm that the cogwheel workshop format (length, set-up, digital system) is satisfactory.
- Other ideas for improvement were more time in the agenda for discussions, earlier announcement of the date and to a larger extent try to avoid overlap with other ongoing arrangements.

Concluding remarks

Thirty respondents were considered as a limited number relative to the number of persons receiving the questionnaire. Still, these thirty respondents represent an important resource for the cogwheel evaluation and number of respondents were considered satisfying. In general, the cogwheel workshop concept seems to fulfil its intention and is considered satisfying. However, there is still a potential in reaching out to more participants in the OHEJP, both regarding input on which external projects to invite and the actual invitation to the cogwheel workshops. Distribution of invitations through the Communication Team in addition to the Project Leaders and deputy Project Leaders has been tested for the 6th cogwheel workshop and will be further followed up on for the final workshops. For the first time, PhD students were also invited to the 6th CW. Since there is a wish for earlier announcement of the dates for CWs, the WP4 cogwheel team will aim for this and also specifically check with the OHEJP projects, suggesting the externally invited project, to avoid overlap with other events. Another observation is to which degree the CWs result in new contacts between OHEJP partners and the invited external projects. Many contacts with other ongoing EU initiatives are made regardless of the CWs, but in average each CW results in one new contact between an OHEJP partner and the external project, which can be considered as a good complement to other contact ways.

One Health EJP Cogwheels Evaluation

1. The aim for cogwheel workshops is to avoid overlaps between external projects and the OHEJP projects and find synergies. Were you aware of this aim before today?

Name	Percent
Yes	83.3%
No	16.7%
N	30

2. Have you been informed about any of the previous cogwheel workshops?

Name	Percent
Yes	83.3%
No	16.7%
N	30

3. Have you been consulted to give in-put for a cogwheel workshop?

Name	Percent
Yes	43.3%
No	56.7%
N	30

4. What is your role in the OHEJP?

Name	Percent
Project leader	23.3%
Deputy project leader	3.3%
Project WP leader	13.3%
Project task leader	16.7%
Other	60.0%
N	30

5. Which cogwheel workshop(s) did you attend?

Name	Percent
No 1 with COMPARE, April 2018	23.3%
No 2 with EFFORT, October 2018	20.0%
No 3 with INNUENDO, IRIDA and COMPARE, September 2019	20.0%
No 4 with INFACIT, January 2020	6.7%
No 5 with JPIAMR, April 2020	33.3%
None	23.3%
N	30

6. Summary of individual responses to “What did you like about the cogwheel(s)?”

The opportunity to get information about important strategic initiatives, the discussions, both the open and closed ones for OHEJP only are appreciated. Further, the good information exchange and knowledge transfer is highlighted and the fact that everyone within OHEJP can participate without any selection. It is underlined that it is not always so easy to find people doing similar things and to know how to approach other projects for contact, and it is appreciated how the cogwheels facilitate this. In some cases the new contacts and knowledge transfer have resulted in specific contributions for the OHEJP projects. Finally, the cogwheels are stated to contribute to general overview of both external projects and within the OHEJP projects.

7. If you have participated in one or more cogwheel workshops, in what way did you find them useful?

Name	Percent
To get information about relating projects	81.8%
To get new contacts for collaboration with one or more of the target projects	63.6%
To avoid overlaps with the project I participate in	36.4%
To build on results from one or more of the target projects	45.5%
Other reason	4.5%
Not usefull	4.5%
N	22

8. Summary of individual answers to the question “For those who answered “not useful” in the previous question - what is the reason you did not find the workshop useful?”

No comments by the respondents were made.

9. Have you contacted any of the invited cogwheel projects after the cogwheel workshop?

Name	Percent
Yes	21.4%
No	78.6%
N	28

10. Summary of individual answers to the question “If you have contacted any of the invited cogwheel projects - was a valuable interaction or future cooperation established? Please specify which of the invited cogwheel project(s) and the respective OHEJP project(s)”

Three respondents confirmed that contact had been made and consequently valuable interactions were established. Projects mentioned were INNUENDO, IRIDA, COMPARE and ORION.

One respondent answered that contact was made with good intentions, but that no cooperation was established.

11. Have you contacted any other EU projects related to the OHEJP, regardless of the cogwheel workshop?

Name	Percent
Yes	44.4%
No	55.6%
N	27

12. Summary of individual answers to the question: “If you have contacted another EU project related to OHEJP, regardless of the cogwheel workshops - was a valuable interaction or future cooperation established? Please specify between which projects”

In addition to using the cogwheel concept, seventeen initiatives for contact with other EU-projects related to OHEJP were registered. Projects mentioned are AVANT, COMPARE, BeOne, ORION, LISTADAPT, COHESIVE, CARE, INNUENDO, ARDIG, WorldCom, SafeConsume, IMPACT, Cost Euro-FBP, NOVA, ADONIS and Tox detect project. Most of the initiatives resulted in valuable interactions, but some of the initiatives also resulted in limited feedback from the targeted project or are yet to be evaluated.

13. Is the format (length, set-up, digital system) of the cogwheels satisfactory?

Name	Percent
Yes	96.0%
No	4.0%
N	25

14. Summary of “If you do not find the cogwheel format satisfactory - how can it be improved?”

No suggestions by the respondents were made.

15. Summary of the question: “Any other ideas about how the cogwheels can be improved?”

It was suggested that it would be nice to know if the cogwheel resulted in actual collaborations and that there should be a bit more time for open discussion and interactions, and less presentations.

Also, it was suggested that the cogwheel dates should be announced a lot earlier to ensure that as many as possible can participate, and so that the OHEJP projects can further distribute the information using their regular sent emails with general information.

Finally, the importance of avoiding overlap with other relevant events was highlighted.